

On the Chemistry of Indian Orchidaceae Plants. Part-III† Dendroflorin, a New Fluorenone Derivative from *Dendrobium densiflorum* Wall.

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Dendroflorin, a new fluorenone derivative has been isolated from *Dendrobium densiflorum* Wall. in addition to dengibsin (1), scopoletin methyl ether, psoralene, oleanolic acid and β -sitosterol. The structure of dendroflorin has been established as 1,2,5-trihydroxy-7-methoxy-9-fluorenone (3) from the spectral properties of itself and its diacetate and triacetate.

UNDER a research programme on the chemical investigation of Indian Orchidaceae plants we studied the orchids *Dendrobium nobile*¹ Lindl. and *Dendrobium gibsonii*² Lindl. The first natural fluorenone derivatives dengibsin (1) and dengibsinin (2) were isolated² from the latter. *Dendrobium densiflorum* Wall., an epiphytic herb, grows in tropical Himalayas³. Earlier work⁴ on the acid hydrolytate of the crude extract of this plant revealed the presence of 4,5-dimethoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid, coumarin, scopoletin methyl ether and ayapin. Reinvestigation on this plant has now resulted in the isolation of a new fluorenone derivative designated dendroflorin (3), along with dengibsin (1), scopoletin methyl ether, psoralene, oleanolic acid and β -sitosterol.

Dendroflorin (3), m.p. 230°, C₁₄H₁₀O₅ (M⁺258), [α]_D²⁰ ± 0°, isolated as red needles from the chloroform extract of the whole orchid, gave positive FeCl₃ colouration and exhibited ir bands [3380(OH) and 1695 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=O)] close to those of 1 and 2. It formed a diacetate (4) (through acetylation of both free phenolic OH groups under mild conditions) and a triacetate (5). The uv and visible spectral data of 3, 4 and 5 (Table 1) resembled closely those of 1, its monoacetate (6) and its diacetate (7)² respectively indicating the presence of a fluorenone chromophore with similar oxygenation pattern. The structure of dendroflorin was establi-

TABLE I—UV AND VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA OF
DENDROFLORIN (3), DENGIBSIN (1) AND
THEIR ACETATE DERIVATIVES

Compound	λ_{max} (EtOH) nm (log ϵ)	λ_{max} (EtOH) nm (log ϵ)
Dendroflorin (3)	259(4.60), 279(4.31), 389.5(4.31) and 485.5 (9.36)	272(4.65) and 520(3.54)
Dengibsin (1)	267(5.36), 275(5.40), 338(4.84) and 479.5(4.08)	291.5(5.45) and 549.5(4.08)
Dendroflorin diacetate (4)	244(4.16), 257(4.15), 272(4.09) and 447(3.20)	—
Dengibsin monoacetate (6)	243(4.29), 260(4.44), 271(4.42), 334(3.64) and 446.5(9.31)	—
Dendroflorin triacetate (5)	258(4.32), 267(4.30), 327.5(3.21) and 424.6(3.26)	—
Dengibsin diacetate (7)	258(4.46), 267(4.47) and 426(2.96)	—

shed from comparative studies on the chemical shifts of its aromatic protons with those of 4 and 5.

† For Parts I and II see Refs. 1 and 2.

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The ^1H nmr spectrum of dendroflorin exhibited signals for one aromatic OCH_3 (δ 4.14, 3H, s), one chelated phenolic OH (δ 8.48, 1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O) and four aromatic protons [δ 6.61 (1H, d, J 9 Hz), 6.92 (1H, d, J 9 Hz) and 6.83 (2H, br s)]; no signal for any of the two free phenolic OH groups was discernible. The two-proton broad singlet at δ 6.83 was due to two *meta*-disposed aromatic protons as evident from the ^1H nmr spectra of 4 and 5 in each of which signals for two *meta*-coupled protons and two *ortho*-coupled protons appeared (Table 2) in conformity with their structures. Dendroflorin is, therefore, a monomethoxy-trihydroxyfluorenone in which one benzene ring bears the *ortho*-disposed protons and the other the *meta*-disposed protons. In dendroflorin diacetate (4) one *ortho*-coupled proton and one *meta*-coupled proton were found to suffer downfield shifts of 0.46 and 0.26 ppm respectively compared to those of dendroflorin (3). Thus, the two free phenolic OH groups are present in two different rings. Since only one *meta*-coupled proton was deshielded on acetylation of the free phenolic OH groups, there should be no OH *meta* to the chelated OH. Hence, the ring bearing the chelated OH contains the *ortho*-disposed protons, *i.e.* the OH groups in this ring would be either 1, 2 or 1, 4. The other ring, which definitely contains the *meta*-disposed protons, could accommodate the free OH only at the 5-position in accordance with the aforesaid arguments. Thus, the structure of dendroflorin should be either 3 or 8. The structure 3 was finally settled from the fact that acetylation of the chelated phenolic OH (by converting 4 to 5) did not cause appreciable deshielding of any aromatic proton (Table 2).

Furthermore, the lower field aromatic proton in the ^1H nmr spectrum of dendroflorin triacetate (5), which is an acetoxy derivative of dengibsin diacetate

(7), appeared at δ 7.13 (d, J 8 Hz). In case of 7, H-2 appeared at δ 7.57 (dd, J 7.5 and 1.5 Hz)², the presence of a *meta*-acetoxy group (*i.e.* at C-4) should not be expected to shield it by $\sim$ 0.45 ppm thus excluding the possibility of structure 8 for dendroflorin. Moreover, structure 8 and also the 1,2,8-trihydroxy-6-methoxy-9-fluorenone structure for dendroflorin contain two chelated OH groups and hence are untenable.

Psoralene was identified from its ir and ^1H nmr spectral data⁵ and the other isolates were characterised by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) with their authentic samples previously isolated in our laboratory^{6,7}.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in an electrical metal bath and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were measured in aldehyde-free ethanol with a Varian 634 S spectrophotometer. The ir spectra were run in KBr pellets or CHCl_3 on either a Pye-Unicam SP 1025 or a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. The ^1H nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 or d_6 -acetone on Varian CFT-20 (80 MHz) or JEOL FX-100 (100 MHz) or Varian XL-200 (200 MHz) spectrometer. The mass spectrum of 3 was run on 70 ev using a direct insertion probe. The silica gel used for column chromatography was of 100-200 mesh, unless otherwise stated, and the tlc experiments were done on silica gel G. Petrol refers to light petroleum, b.p. 60-80°.

Extraction: Air-dried and powdered whole plant *D. densiflorum* (1 kg), collected from Darjeeling District, was extracted in Soxhlet apparatus with

TABLE 2— ^1H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF DENDROFLORIN (3), ITS DIACETATE (4) AND TRIACETATE (5)^a

Compd. no.	Chemical shifts (δ), multiplicities and coupling constants (Hz)							
	$\text{C}_1 - \text{OH}/\text{OCOCH}_3^b$	$\text{C}_2 - \text{OH}/\text{OCOCH}_3^b$	H-5	H-4	$\text{C}_6 - \text{OH}/\text{OCOCH}_3^b$	H-6	$\text{C}_7 - \text{OCH}_3$	H-8
3	8.48 ^c	—	6.61, d (9)	6.92, d (9)	—	6.83, bs	4.14	6.83, bs
4	9.01 ^c	2.88	7.07, d (8)	6.83, d (8)	2.44	7.09, d (2)	4.12	6.87, d (2)
5	2.24	2.28	7.13, d (8)	6.91, d (8)	2.32	7.05, d (2)	3.84	6.83, d (2)

^a For 3, 80 MHz, d_6 -acetone; for 4, 200 MHz, CDCl_3 and for 5, 100 MHz, CDCl_3 .

^b The assignment of the OCOCH_3 signals of 4 and 5 may be interchanged.

^c Disappeared on deuteration.

petrol and chloroform in succession for 40 h each. The concentrates of the extracts were chromatographed separately over silica gel (60-100 mesh) using solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity as eluents.

Compounds from petrol extract :

β -Sitosterol : The early petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates afforded β -sitosterol (0.005%), m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample 137°; $[\alpha]_D - 37^\circ$ (CHCl₃).

Psoralene : The later petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates on rechromatography over silica gel furnished psoralene (0.001%), crystallising from chloroform-petrol in colourless needles, m.p. 160°.

Scopoletin methyl ether : The concentrate of the petrol-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) eluates on rechromatography over silica gel afforded scopoletin methyl ether (0.003%), crystallising from chloroform-petrol in colourless needles, m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample 143°.

Oleanolic acid : The concentrate of the petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluates on repeated chromatography over silica gel furnished oleanolic acid (0.001%), m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample 304°; acetate, m.p. 260°, $[\alpha]_D + 71.4^\circ$ (CHCl₃).

Compounds from the chloroform extract :

Dengibsin (1) : The concentrate of the early petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluates on rechromatography over silica gel furnished dengibsin (1) (0.001%), crystallising from acetone-petrol in deep red needles, m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample 227°.

Dendroflorin (3) : The concentrate of the later petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluates on repeated chromatography over silica gel afforded dendroflorin (3) (0.0004%), crystallising from acetone-petrol in red needles, m.p. 230°; green colouration with FeCl₃ solution; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3380, 1695, 1630, 1520 and 1295 cm⁻¹; m/z 258 (M⁺, 92.2%), 243 (100), 215 (22), 187 (8.3), 137 (8.0) and 129 (7.9).

Dendroflorin diacetate (4) : To a solution of dendroflorin (3) (2 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) 2 drops of a solution of Ac₂O in pyridine (prepared by adding 2 drops of Ac₂O to 1 ml pyridine) was added at 0° and the mixture was kept in the deep freeze for 17 h. Usual work up of the reaction mixture furnished dendroflorin diacetate (4), crystallising from chloroform-petrol in orange needles (2 mg), m.p. 168°; $\nu_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 3320, 1768, 1712, 1605, 1520, 1425, 1225, 1205, 1015 and 930 cm⁻¹.

Dendroflorin triacetate (5) : Dendroflorin diacetate (4) (2 mg) was acetylated (Ac₂O/Py, 24 h) at room temperature and the product was crystallised from chloroform-petrol to afford dendroflorin triacetate (5) as yellow needles (1.5 mg), m.p. 172°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1760, 1712, 1610, 1485, 1368, 1305, 1195, 1185, 1020 and 900 cm⁻¹.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Mr. D. F. Dance (Stirling University, U. K.) for mass spectral measurements, and to Professor U. R. Ghatak (I.A.C.S., Calcutta) and Dr. A. K. Chakraborty (I.I.C.B., Calcutta) for ¹H nmr spectra. Financial assistance from U.G.C., New Delhi by way of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of the authors (S.B.) is gratefully acknowledged.

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